

GREEN HYDROGEN : A NEW ALTERNATIVE GREEN ENERGY IN NORTH BENGAL, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Green Hydrogen is produced by the process of electrolysis, where water is split into hydrogen and oxygen using electricity generated from renewable energy sources like solar, wind, hydropower or the like. In the present work determination of efficiency of fuel cell is carried out considering that the fuel cell can be produced using 'green' hydrogen as a fuel for power generation and other uses in North Bengal, the Northern part of West Bengal, India. Green hydrogen fuel cells are an emerging renewable energy technology with the potential to serve as a sustainable power generation and for other related uses. Challenges related to green hydrogen production are explained. It has been shown water of many of the rivers in North Bengal is conducive for ready electrolysis to generate hydrogen. Further it is shown that renewable energy like hydro-electric, solar energy and to some small extent wind energy apart from energy from bio-mass can be harnessed in North Bengal. With this, by electrolysis of river water, 'green hydrogen' generation is feasible in North Bengal and this can be a promising green energy here.

KEYWORDS: Green Hydrogen, Efficiency, North Bengal, River

1 INTRODUCTION

Energy is the driving force of civilization. The demand for power-generation systems of high efficiency with low emission is of increasing importance. Green Hydrogen is a promising alternative in this regard. It is produced by the process of electrolysis, where water is split into hydrogen and oxygen using electricity generated from renewable energy sources like solar, wind, hydropower or the like. Green energy can be used to develop fuel cells and the fuel cell (FC) is regarded as an enabling clean energy technology with a great potential worldwide because it can convert the chemical energy of the fuel directly to energy and can theoretically achieve a high electrical efficiency. Hydrogen fuel cells are a compelling alternative for power generation, offering a clean and sustainable energy source. They hold the potential to replace traditional fossil fuel-based power systems in various applications, addressing both environmental and energy security concerns. They provide a good alternative against conventional renewable energy such as biogas which may not be sufficient to power large industrial belts or large cities with huge power requirement. Intense research is going on this subject and new findings and development avenues are coming out. Some papers in this regard may be referred here like by Le T.T. et al. (2024), by Zainal et al. (2024), by Yin, S. (2025), by Wang C. et al. (2024), by Taheri A. H and Ardehali M. M. (2025) and others.

2 DETERMINATION OF EFFICIENCY

One measure of efficiency of hydrogen fuel cell is simply the practical cell-output voltage divided by the thermodynamically reversible voltage at the stated temperature and pressure of operation. For purposes of calculating overall energy efficiencies, it is necessary to compare the electrical output of the cell stack (in joules) with the enthalpy of the cell reaction, which for hydrogen fuel equates to the heat of formation of water. There are two values of this function: (i) a higher heating value (HHV), which corresponds to the

product water being present as liquid; (ii) a lower heating value (LHV), which applies when the product water is present as uncondensed vapour or steam. In a low-temperature fuel cell, where the product is liquid water, the HHV should be employed in efficiency calculations, while for high-temperature fuel cells it may be permissible to use the LHV if the product steam is put to good use. The efficiency of any energy conversion device is defined as the ratio between useful energy output and energy input.

$$\eta = \text{actual electrical work}/\text{maximum available work} = \Delta G^\circ / \Delta H^\circ$$

where, (ΔG°) is the change in Gibb's free energy i.e., the electrical work the fuel cell produces & (ΔH°) is the change in enthalpy of the system i.e., the heating value of the fuel.

$$= (\Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S) / \Delta H^\circ = 1 - (T\Delta S / \Delta H^\circ)$$

(where T is the absolute temperature of formation of water and ΔS is the entropy for formation of water).

Hence, the maximum possible thermodynamic efficiency of a fuel cell can be written as,

$$\eta = 1 - (T\Delta S / \Delta H^\circ)$$

Thermodynamic efficiency can be defined as the ratio of work output to heat energy input in a heat engine system. For thermodynamic efficiency for hydrogen fuel cell is expressed as $= (\Delta G^\circ / \Delta H^\circ) \times 100$

$$(\Delta G_f^\circ) = -237.1 \text{ kJ/mol (For HHV)} \ \& \ -228.6 \text{ kJ/mol (For LHV)}$$

$$(\Delta H_f^\circ) = -285.8 \text{ kJ/mol (For HHV)} \ \& \ -241.8 \text{ kJ/mol (For LHV)}$$

In the case of a fuel cell, the useful energy output is the electrical energy produced, and the energy input is the enthalpy (h) of hydrogen, that is, hydrogen's HHV. Assuming that all of the Gibbs free energy can be converted into electrical energy (the reaction is reversible), the maximum theoretical efficiency of a fuel cell is called 'Thermodynamic efficiency(η)' $= (-237.34) / (-286.02) \times 100 = 83\%$

For hydrogen's LHV, the fuel cell efficiency would be :

$$\text{Thermodynamic efficiency}(\eta) = (-228.74) / (-241.98) \times 100 = 94.5\% \text{ (as shown in Lindiwe Khotseng, 2019)}$$

.The LHV has higher efficiency compared to HHV, because the reversible efficiency of the fuel cell decreases as the operating temperature increases. The expected fuel cell efficiency is not always achieved due to thermodynamic and electrochemical irreversible losses.

3 IRREVERSIBLE LOSS

In practice, the thermodynamic cell potential is decreased from its ideal potential, usually less than 1 Volt (V), due to irreversible losses known as over potential or polarisation. The fuel cell performance over potential is due to :

a) Activation over potential: Activation losses are caused by the energy required to initiate the electrochemical reaction. The activation polarisation is related to the charge transfer processes occurring during the electrochemical reactions on electrode surface

$$V_{\text{activation}} = (RT / \alpha nF) \ln(I / I_0)$$

where ,

$V_{\text{activation}}$: Voltage loss due to activation

R : Universal gas constant

T : Absolute temperature (Kelvin)

α : Charge transfer coefficient (usually between 0.2 and 0.5)

n : Number of electrons transferred per reaction (2 for hydrogen fuel cells)

F : Faraday's constant

I : Current density

I_0 : Exchange current density

b) Ohmic over potential: In most fuel cells, the most important contribution to this resistance is the electrolyte, due to the ionic nature of its conductivity, resistance to the flow of electrons through the electrodes and the contact resistance at the cell terminals.

$$V_{\text{ohmic}} = I \cdot R_{\text{ohmic}}$$

where, I : Current density

R_{ohmic} : Total resistance due to ions and electrons

3. Mass transport (concentration) over potential: Concentration polarisation occurs due to a decrease in the concentration of the reactants at the electrode electrolyte interface.

$$V_{concentration} = RT/nF[(I_{lim})/(I_{lim}-I)]$$

where, R : Universal gas constant

T : Absolute temperature (Kelvin)

n : Number of electrons transferred per reaction (2 for hydrogen fuel cells)

F : Faraday's constant

I : Current density

I_{lim} : Limiting current density

The standard measure of performance is the polarisation curve, which represents the cell voltage behaviour against operating current density. From the Figure 1, the voltage loss caused by mixed potential and crossover, activation polarisation, ohmic polarisation and mass transport losses is the most significant in the tail of the I-V curve. The maximum fuel cell is then examined through the reversible voltage of the system, which is calculated using thermodynamics and the actual voltage of the system. The final voltage is lower than the thermodynamic voltage and is usually between 0.5 and 1.0 V. Although polarisations cannot be eliminated, material choice and electrode designs can contribute to their minimisation.

Figure 1. H_2/O_2 polarisation curve at equilibrium and voltage losses in fuel cell, taken from Khotseng, L.(2019)

$$\text{Thus, } E(\text{cell potential}) = E_{\text{thermodynamic}} - V_{\text{activation}} - V_{\text{ohmic}} - V_{\text{concentration}}$$

where , $E_{\text{thermodynamic}}$ = thermodynamic potential

$V_{\text{activation}}$ = voltage loss due to activation polarisation

V_{ohmic} = voltage loss due to ohmic polarisation

$V_{\text{concentration}}$ = voltage loss due to mass transport polarisation

and, the entropy generation $S = E/nFT$

4 GREEN HYDROGEN STORAGE AND CHALLENGES

Hydrogen storage and transportation methods in the development process have to be economical and efficient. Two such methods are: storing hydrogen either in materials or in containers. Hydrogen could be stored in containers in both compressed and liquid forms. The compressed hydrogen storage method involves storing hydrogen under high pressure as a gas. In contrast, it is kept in liquid form using the liquid hydrogen storage method. Like any gas, hydrogen can also be compressed and stored in tanks, and then used as needed. However, the volume of hydrogen is much larger than that of other hydrocarbons — nearly four times as much as natural gas. Compressed hydrogen gas has some striking features, like a quick refuelling capacity, excellent latent characteristics, and minimal impact on infrastructure.

One of the primary challenges before the hydrogen energy developers is the high cost of producing and storing hydrogen. Currently, the cost of producing and storing hydrogen is more than that of conventional fossil fuels. This is a big challenge for the researchers. They have to invent advanced befitting methodologies to cut down the cost of hydrogen generation and storage. Another challenging issue is related to shortage of infrastructure for hydrogen energy, such as hydrogen refueling stations and storage facilities.

5 SCOPE FOR NORTH BENGAL TO PRODUCE GREEN HYDROGEN

There are a lot of rivers in North Bengal, like the Teesta, Torsha, Mahananda, Jaldhaka, Raidhak and many others and their tributaries. The rivers mostly originated from the Himalayan or sub-Himalayan regions. These rivers typically have slightly alkaline pH due to mineral dissolution from rocks (e.g., limestone or other carbonates) and also industrial pollution is quite less here, due to less industrialization in the northern zone of West Bengal. Overall, the river water in North Bengal is mostly neutral to slightly alkaline. Again, alkaline water electrolysis (AWE) is one of the most practical and advanced technologies and this has a long history of utilization in the chlor-alkali industry for large-scale hydrogen production. In fact, alkaline water electrolysis (AWE) is a mature and available hydrogen production technology and there exist a number of economic assessments in this regard (Kuckshinrichs et al., 2017). Thus North Bengal river water is quite conducive for producing hydrogen by electrolysis. Again most of the large rivers of this zone have strong currents, particularly in hilly areas, and from this hydro-electric generation is possible and in fact, is being produced. This is a renewable form of energy. There are many fountains in hills having violently fast streams from which micro-scale hydro-electric power can be generated. Further electric power can be generated from solar energy and in some locations from small-scale wind mills too. Therefore, in North Bengal using renewable power 'green hydrogen' generation is quite possible and thereby, fuel cell also. This offers a promising possible renewable source of energy in North Bengal.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In the present investigation the basic concept of green hydrogen is placed at first. Determination of efficiency of fuel cell and irreversible losses are carried out, considering that green hydrogen can be used in developing fuel cell. The challenges related to green hydrogen use are noted down. It has been identified that many river water in North Bengal are quite conducive for hydrogen production by electrolysis process. Various possible natural sources of renewable energies in North Bengal are also identified. Thus possibility of generation of green hydrogen in North Bengal by river water aided with available renewable energy is established. This can be a good green energy source in North Bengal.

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